

Is Newa The Answer to North Badung Tourism Development?

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ABSTRACT: Badung has many tourism destinations and cultures that are the mainstay of Bali tourism. Measuring from the Gross Regional Domestic Product, it can be said that this Regency is the largest economic contributor in the tourism sector. The existence of the COVID-19 Pandemic has caused the downfall of various sectors, including the tourism industry. Regional Regulation No. 6 of 2020 concerning Strengthening the Tourism Sector Program of Badung Regency aims to increase the competitiveness of tourism in synergy with cross-sectors. This policy is expected to increase innovative tourism development and provide welfare for communities around tourist destinations.

This research was conducted in the northern region of Badung Regency using qualitative methods with qualitative data types that use purposive sampling as a way to obtain appropriate research informants. There are data sources in the form of primary data sourced from the results of in-depth interviews and observations and secondary data sources derived from policy documents, scientific articles and reports.

The results of this study indicate that strengthening development in Badung Regency can be seen from its shortcomings and advantages through the policy implementation process. The northern Badung region, which is still far below the southern Badung region, requires better coordination with other stakeholders, especially with the implementation of NEWA-based tourism that is in accordance with tourism development in this region.

KEYWORDS: Policy implementation, tourism development, NEWA

INTRODUCTION

Tourism development has an impact not only on tourist areas but also on the surrounding environment. The increase in the number of tourist visits when viewed from an economic perspective will increase the income of tourism actors. The success of tourism development and development is highly dependent on many things. In its implementation, there are several obstacles that are often encountered and if not considered, they can later hinder tourism development itself. Badung Regency is one of the largest economic contributors in Bali through its tourism sector. This can be measured through the Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) in 2023 where as a tourist destination, the Transportation and warehousing category as a provider of access for tourists is the largest producer, namely 37.97 percent of the total GRDP. Provision of Accommodation and Food and Beverages is the second pillar of the Badung Regency economy at 24.67 percent of the total GRDP of Badung Regency. In addition to being the highest contributor to the Badung Regency economy, the Transportation and Warehousing provision category is also recorded to have growth above 5 percent in 2023 (BPS Kabupaten Badung, 2024).

Tourism development in a destination can be measured through its development stages. An article on the development of tourism in Badung Regency has been compiled by (Mahagangga et al., 2021) using the concept of tourism morphosis, namely the concept of tourism evolution as a process of tourism development in tourist destinations. The results of this study are described in the form of a table, where currently tourism in Badung Regency is at the compromise stage from 2012 to the present, after going through several previous stages, namely the introduction stage, reaction stages, institutionalization stage stages 1, 2 and 3 where at each stage there are differences in periods, paradigms, actors, discourses and supporting institutions.

In the Renstra (Strategic Plan) of the Badung Regency Tourism Office, it is stated that there are several strategic issues regarding the implementation of spatial planning in Badung Regency, namely 1) the imbalance in the development of the Southern Badung region with the Northern Badung Region, because the basic potential they have requires integrated management that is synergistic and mutually supportive between sub-districts, 2) the development of new urban areas, with the Badung Government Center in the Sempidi area and the Mengwi urban area has been designated as the Capital City of Badung Regency, and 3) the inclusion of 5 sub-districts as part of the Sarbagita Metropolitan area which requires cross-regional development coordination.

Referring to the Renstra of the Badung Regency Tourism Office, it is necessary to conduct a policy evaluation to carry out equitable development and development priorities in each region.

Another challenge in tourism development is the management of tourism resources, innovation, human resources, infrastructure and the Covid-19 pandemic that occurred some time ago (Yuda Pratama, 2023). The real impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic has hit tourism development in Badung Regency, where most of the people work in this industrial sector. During the COVID-19 pandemic that began in 2020, there was a very drastic decrease in the number of tourists. Based on data from UNWTO, in early 2021 there was a decrease in the number of international tourists by 87 percent compared to January 2020. The people of Badung, both those who work directly and indirectly in the tourism sector, have felt the impact of this pandemic, including layoffs (PHK), decreased income and so on. The steps taken by the Badung Tourism Office in overcoming this pandemic problem are to optimize promotions through the distribution of promotions by bringing in the millennial generation who already have many followers on their social media who act as celebrities, YouTubers and TikTokers. Promotion is also carried out through online media such as the Tourism Information System (SITA), the Tourism Office's social media accounts and inviting the media to cover tourism activities, inviting students and local communities to promotional activities carried out during the pandemic (Selamet et al., 2022).

Tourism products that have high tourism appeal with high selling value are something that must be considered by stakeholders. Tourism that is very vulnerable to change requires precise and fast thinking so that it can meet the desires and expectations of tourists. One of the breakthroughs initiated by the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy is tourism with the concept of Nature, Ecotourism, Wellness and Adventure (NEWA) which is the answer to the needs of tourists after the COVID-19 pandemic. The development of NEWA-based tourism is very likely to be accelerated through a more integrated approach between concepts holistically, which ultimately can create more authentic tourism offerings with unique appeal (Wulandari, 2024). One of the health tourism programs implemented in Bali is wellness tourism with Balinese characteristics, involving the local community more comprehensively and emphasizing the principles of sustainable tourism. One of these principles is determining leading tourism products that are unique to Bali and reflect local Balinese wisdom (Ratna et al., 2022). Furthermore, good management of tourist destinations is needed to create loyal tourists due to satisfaction after visiting and carrying out activities at tourist destinations (Ambarawati et al., 2024).

Based on the development problems as mentioned above, it is necessary to take a policy that can help the Regional Government to improve the quality of tourism in its area. Regional Regulation No. 6 of 2020 concerning Strengthening the Tourism Sector Program was ratified as a direction, basis and legal certainty in the development of tourism in Badung Regency. The implementation of this policy is expected to be able to increase the competitiveness of tourism so that it can increase the number of tourist visits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research was conducted in Badung Regency, specifically in the northern part, due to the imbalance in tourism development between the north and south of Badung. The qualitative method used in this article employs qualitative data and primary data sources obtained from in-depth interviews and observations at the research site. Secondary data sources were obtained from policy documents, previous research, and reports compiled by relevant agencies such as the Regional Tourism Office.

Informants were selected using purposive sampling, which is the selection of informants based on specific objectives and considerations, such as Badung Regional Government employees, tourism practitioners, and members of the community who are involved in tourism. According to (Creswell, 2018) data collection techniques were conducted through in-depth interviews, observations, and literature reviews. Research instruments included interview guidelines and participatory observation. Data presentation was carried out through several stages, including data reduction, data display, and drawing conclusions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Implementation of Regional Regulation Policy No. 6 of 2020 concerning Strengthening the Tourism Sector Program in North Badung Regency

Regional development through the tourism sector is one of the programs that has been prepared because it is seen as having a strategic role in advancing community welfare and strengthening the implementation of regional autonomy. The existence of a policy will be a good foundation if it is implemented in accordance with the regulations that have been set. Mazmanian and Sabatier

in (Wahab, 2016) define implementation as understanding what actually happens after a program is declared valid or formulated as the focus of attention for policy implementation, namely events and activities that arise after the ratification of public policy guidelines which include both efforts to administer it and to cause real consequences/impacts on society or events.

The dimensions of policy implementation according to (Mthethwa, 2012) begin with Policy formulation and dissemination. The description of this is as follows:

A. Policy Formulation

1) Scope of policy issues

- a) CHAPTER I, General Provisions consisting of Articles 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5
- b) CHAPTER II, Strengthening the Tourism Sector Program consisting of Part One General in Article 6, Part Two Objectives in Article 7, Part Three Targets in Article 8, Part Four Strategy in Article 9. Part Five is Article 10 and Part Six is Budget Allocation stated in Article 10
- c) CHAPTER III, Community Role stated in Article 12
- d) CHAPTER IV, Guidance and Supervision stated in Article 13
- e) CHAPTER V, Funding stated in Article 14
- f) CHAPTER VI, Closing Provisions stated through Article 15

2) Policy objectives

Regional Regulation No. 6 of 2020 concerning Strengthening Tourism Sector Programs as one of the supporters of development implementation in Badung Regency. The existence of this policy aims to increase the competitiveness of tourism in synergy with cross-sectors such as agriculture, fisheries, maritime and creative economy. Given that tourism is a multidimensional activity, it is hoped that tourism can be a potential driver that can later support tourism in Badung Regency

3) Policy Goals

Strengthening the tourism sector has several strategic targets that need to be improved to obtain high selling value based on the potential of each sector with policy targets aimed at tourism destination managers, surrounding communities and also in order to increase Regional Original Income. The targets are:

- a) Increasing competitive and sustainable DTW
- b) Increasing the number of foreign tourist visits
- c) Increasing the synergy between tourism and agriculture
- d) Increasing the number of sustainable coastal areas to support marine tourism

4) Members of the community who receive benefits

The goal of implementing this policy is to improve community welfare. The community in this regulation consists of local communities in tourism destinations who work in supporting sectors such as homestay owners, local tour guides, artists and cultural actors, as well as farmers and fishermen. Income from tourism will also be indirectly felt by the entire community in Badung Regency through activities carried out by the Badung Regency Government.

5) General actions and strategies for solving problems

The Badung Regency Government has outlined a strategy to strengthen the Tourism Sector Program through:

- a) Organizing DTW based on traditional village communities, culture and Balinese nature
- b) Implementing and setting hotel tariffs rationally and healthily for the common good
- c) Strengthening DTW management institutions
- d) Increasing sustainable tourism marketing
- e) Increasing the quality of the creative economy-based tourism industry
- f) Increasing the quality and quantity of tourism support facilities in tourist villages
- g) Increasing coastal areas that are sustainable and beneficial for the community

6) Implementation time scope

Strengthening the Tourism Sector Program jointly approved by the Badung Regency Regional People's Representative Council and the Badung Regent is manifested in the form of a policy instrument containing one or more programs to achieve the targets and objectives of regional development in an effort to ensure community welfare. This policy has been in effect since it was stipulated and enacted on June 15, 2020 until now.

7) Reasons for policy making

The Regional Regulation on strengthening the tourism program was formulated by looking at the latest conditions of tourism in Badung Regency. With the rapid changes and demands for innovation in the tourism sector, it is hoped that there will be a strengthening of the Regional Government in organizing activities in the tourism sector so that they can be carried out sustainably and in line with the programs that have been set by the Government at the Bali Provincial level effectively and efficiently.

B. Dissemination

1) Activities

Activities that can be carried out by the Badung Regency Regional Government to improve tourism in the Regency include the following:

- a) The development of tourist destinations based on village potential is realized by the development of tourist villages. In accordance with the latest tourism concept that is in demand after the COVID-19 pandemic, it is called Nature, Ecotourism, Wellness and Adventure (NEWA) Tourism. The existence of tourism activities with this concept has resulted in several places being transformed into tourist destinations such as the melukat place at Griya Beji Waterfall located in Punggul Village, Badung Regency and Pancoran Solas.
- b) To avoid unhealthy competition in the accommodation sector, the Bali Provincial Tourism Office has drafted regulations, namely the Draft Governor's Regulation (Ranpergub) on Bali Tourism Governance. These regulations will be monitored by several tourism offices in determining the price range for hotels, thus facilitating tourism supervision and commerce (Gorda & Sudharma, 2023)
- c) Training and empowerment of human resources that handle tourism affairs can be done with the aim of improving the quality of individuals and strengthening tourism institutions. Qualified hard skills and soft skills are obtained through training and workshop activities held by related agencies such as the Badung Regency Tourism Office and academics. Procurement of competency certification is also one way to improve the quality of service. Standardization that must be met by tourism destinations including hotel and restaurant managers, for example Cleanliness, Health, Safety and Environment Sustainability (CHSE) is carried out so that tourists feel safe and protected when traveling.
- d) Promotional activities carried out by the relevant Department are carried out consistently and more precisely. The development of technology causes news or information about a tourist destination to spread faster than using print media. Thus, it is necessary to have a bait in the form of interesting news or content so that tourists want to visit

2) Achievement indicators

Indicators of achievement of Regional Regulation No. 6 of 2020 concerning Strengthening Tourism Sector Programs can be seen from various aspects such as:

- a) Economic Aspect: strengthening the tourism program in Badung Regency can be seen from the increase in tourism's contribution to Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP). Data from the Central Statistics Agency of Badung Regency, in 2023 the Transportation and Warehousing category as tourist entry access contributed 27.97% and was followed by the Accommodation and Food and Beverage Provision category reaching 24.7%. The amount in 2023 increased from 2022 by 7.21 percent in the Transportation and Warehousing sector and 1.1 percent in the Accommodation and Food and Beverage Provision sector.
- b) Tourism Visit Aspect: Accommodation is one of the mandatory needs for tourists during a tourist trip. Based on data collected by the Central Statistics Agency of Badung Regency, there has been an increase in the room occupancy rate and average stay at hotels and other accommodation services. In 2022, the number of star hotels was 27% of the total, namely 380 hotels and non-star hotels as many as 73% or 1,042 with the room occupancy rate at star hotels being 36.14% and 21.05% and the rest is other types of accommodation. The occupancy rate of star hotels is 36.09 and non-star 15.01. The average stay of foreign guests at star hotels is 2.63 or 2-3 days and 2.85 or 2.5 days at non-star hotels. Domestic tourists also spend an average of 2.0 days staying at hotels, both starred and non-starred. The distribution of the number of hotels, both starred and non-starred, in Badung Regency has increased by 27% of starred hotels, equivalent to 413 hotels, and 73% of non-starred hotels or 1,132. The room occupancy rate has also increased along with the increasing number of tourists visiting Bali. In 2023, the room occupancy rate was 52.88% in

starred hotels and 32.64% in non-starred hotels. The average foreign guest stay in a starred hotel is 2.88 days while domestic is 2.13 days, in non-starred hotels the average foreign guest stay is 2.60 and for domestic guests is 1.57 days.

c) Dissemination Process

The process of disseminating Regional Regulation No. 6 of 2020 concerning Strengthening Tourism Sector Programs through several stages such as socialization carried out by the relevant Agency to tourism industry players, the general public and other related organizations. Information regarding policies can also be done through training so that later participants will better understand the implementation and evaluation procedures. The media that can be used to disseminate this Regulation can be in the form of print but the most widely used today is electronic.

Implementation of Nature, Ecotourism, Wellness and Adventure (NEWA) based tourism in the northern part of Badung Regency

North Badung Regency is one of the areas that focuses on natural tourism in the form of plantations which can then be developed as agro tourism. According to Mr. Agung Adi who is the Head of the Tourism Institution Section, stated that "The tourism potential owned by Badung Regency is very different on both sides. North Badung as the upstream of tourism, in Balinese beliefs the upstream is the source of life so that many in the north are mountains and water sources that make the community's plantations fertile. On the other hand, South Badung is the downstream of tourism, where in the Balinese concept it is the place where the water flow ends, so what is in the south is the beach". Thus it is clear that the type of tourism developed will be very different.

Tourism development in North Badung tends to be slower than South Badung. Although culturally and naturally beautiful, both areas have high value when viewed from the perspective of attractions as tourist attractions, the striking difference lies in accessibility and amenities. Ngurah Rai International Airport is located in South Badung, so tourist accessibility is easy, as are the diverse and spread out accommodations in this area. The development of North Badung in the accommodation sector is by building homestays or budget hotels, considering that the tourism potential offered is more towards nature and culture. Tourism villages are one type of tourism developed in the north because they are considered in accordance with the concept of sustainability and community empowerment. The trend that is the mainstay when the COVID-19 pandemic ends is tourism activities related to nature-based sustainability, ecotourism, fitness and adventure or what is commonly called Nature, Ecotourism, Wellness and Adventure (NEWA) (Kardianto et al., 2024).

Based on observations that have been made, there are several potentials that North Badung has that can be developed into NEWA-based tourism, namely:

A. Belok Sidan

Belok Sidan Village is one of the tourist villages included in the pioneering category with tourist attractions in the form of natural tourist attractions, namely Pancoran Air Panas, Tukad Bangkung waterfall, Ayung River, rice fields, hills, forests and asparagus plantations. Amenities in the form of accommodation in the form of homestays, villas and tourist cottages are available in this village. For places to eat, there are several stalls and places to eat located in the surrounding area which are easy to find. Access to visit Belok Sidan Village is relatively good, as evidenced by the road that is equipped with directions and also the road conditions are adequate. Supporting institutions are the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis) and the Village-Owned Enterprise (Bumdes). This potential can be developed into NEWA with the following classifications:

- Nature in the form of natural scenery including rice fields, hills and Tukad Bangkung waterfall
- Ecotourism in the form of asparagus agrotourism located in Belok Sidan Village
- Wellness in the form of hot water baths that can provide relaxation for tourists
- Adventure can be done by cycling along village roads and soft trekking in rice field and forest areas

B. Pelaga

Pelaga Village is located in Petang District and is also included in the category of tourist villages. The famous tourist attraction in this area is Nung-nung Waterfall. Amenities in the form of accommodation are available although the number is not too much, while for places to eat are available next to the Tukad Bangkung bridge. Accessibility to Pelaga Village is relatively good with adequate road conditions, easy access with digital maps and clear directions to find this village. Institutionally, tourism activities have been well coordinated between Pokdarwis, the Head of the Tourism Village and Karang Taruna (the

village youth group). NEWA-based tourism that can be found in this village can be said to be centered on Nung-nung Waterfall, where the natural scenery around it is very attractive, wellness and adventure can be found in soft trekking activities to the waterfall location and when bathing under the natural waterfall.

C. Petang

Petang Village is one of the villages that has various kinds of tourist attractions that can be developed through NEWA-based tourism. Accessibility to this village is good, directions to tourist destinations are available and electronic maps can be used to reach this place. Accommodation in this village is in the form of homestays and villas managed by the private sector. The institutions that manage tourism are the Tourism Awareness Group (Pokdarwis) and the Village-Owned Enterprise (Bumdes). The tourist attractions that can be developed are as follows:

- a) Nature: Bidadari Ayung Petang waterfall is a natural waterfall
- b) Ecotourism: Pura Puncak Tedung which is a place of worship for Hindus that has spiritual and cultural values
- c) Adventure: rafting activities that can be done on the Ayung River

D. Carangsari

Carangsari Village is one of the popular tourist destinations in North Badung. Accessibility in the form of good road conditions, availability of road signs to tourist destinations. The accommodation found in this village is also diverse such as villas and homestays, places to eat available in the form of food stalls and restaurants as well as Balinese souvenir shops. The potential tourist attractions that have been developed are as follows:

- a) Nature: natural scenery that can be enjoyed throughout the village such as rice fields and rivers
- b) Ecotourism: Beji Park which is one of the environmental conservation areas
- c) Wellness: there are several places that offer health programs that combine elements of Balinese culture with health practices such as yoga and meditation
- d) Adventure: one of the famous attractions in this area is rafting on the Ayung River.

CONCLUSIONS

Tourism is one of the sensitive service industries so that it requires speed and accuracy of management of the Regional Government in carrying out innovation in tourism development. The policies taken must be implemented with a qualified evaluation and monitoring dissertation. The development of NEWA-based tourism is one of the activities that is growing rapidly in tourism in North Badung. The development and construction of natural and cultural potential is carried out by looking at the potential that is owned so that later North Badung will not only be a supporter of South Badung tourism, but also as an exclusive tourist destination with high competitiveness.

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